

Distance Mode of Education: Navigating Challenges and Building Strengths

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Abstract

Generally, the educational process has been dominated by two modes of education viz. face-to-face education and distance education. Both modes of education may have an impact on the academic performance of students. The present study focuses on strengthening the distance education mode for the enhancement of overall academic growth of learners. As distance education has revolutionized the whole learning process and provided opportunities for the students to access education from anywhere and at any time, this paper studies the concept, historical perspective, attributes, challenges, and strategies to strengthen distance education. The historical background of distance education highlights its development and transition from correspondence education to Information Communication Technology (ICT) based education. The attributes of distance education include accessibility, flexibility, affordability, and personalization that enables students to learn according to their own needs. However, distance mode of education poses certain challenges to learners that affect their academic achievement. Apart from infrastructural and technological challenges, the lack of face-to-face interaction that many times leads to lack of clarity of complex concepts among the learners. To meet these challenges, certain strategies including technical support, utilization of online resources, updating learning materials, proper library support system, and effective personal contact programmes should be followed. Thus, the present study may contribute to the field of distance education and support its growth by proposing certain strategies to strengthen it for the better academic performance of the learners.

Keywords: Distance mode of education, Distance learning, ICT, Challenges

Introduction

Ever since the formalization of the institution of examination, it has played a key role in influencing the educational process as well as classifying students for various purposes. Because of this, it has attracted the attention of all those who are linked with the planning and decision-making process in the education system. The researchers being interested in exploring different factors related to the examination system have investigated various aspects of the system viz. prescribed syllabus, teaching methods, medium of instruction, nature of examination, semester vs. annual system, nature of question paper etc. They have found that all these factors affect the performance of the students in the examination. Besides, the mode of education or the learning environment, i.e., conventional face-to-face education and distance education may also be affecting the achievement level of the students. Omoniyi-Esan et. al. (2022) found the learning environment to be one of the factors affecting students' academic success. According to Fozdar & Kumar 2007, distance learners tend to experience lower levels of academic achievement and retention compared to their on-campus counterparts. Several factors contribute to this difference, including age, socio-economic

background, and social circumstances such as limited support and feelings of isolation. Ai-Qahtani (2015) mentioned that the students’ approaches to studying and their educational environment affects academic outcomes such as academic achievement, wellbeing, social emotional adjustment, and self-esteem of the students. Identifying the significance of distance education as a valuable mode of education, the Government of India has framed various policies to support it. The regulatory bodies like “University Grants Commission (UGC)” have played a significant role in regulating the standards and quality of education offered through distance education mode, and in ensuring that the quality is comparable to that of face-to-face traditional programmes. It is generally believed that conventional classroom education is better than distance education as there is continuous face-to-face teacher-student interaction in the former system. That's why it is needed to strengthen the distance mode of education. And on these grounds the present study has been undertaken.

Conceptual framework of distance education

Different researchers/organizations conceptualized distance education in their own ways. Some of these are described in the following. Holmberg (1989) defined distance education as “a method of imparting knowledge, skills, and attitudes which is rationalized by the application of division of labor and organizational principles as well as by the extensive use of technical media, especially for the purpose of reproducing high quality teaching material which makes it possible to instruct great numbers of students at the same time wherever they live. It is an industrialized form of teaching and learning”. As per “UNESCO” (2002) “distance education is any educational process in which all or most of the teaching is conducted by someone removed in space and/or time from the learner, with the effect that all or most of the communication between teachers and learners is through an artificial medium, either electronic or print”. Moore & Kearsley (2011) defined distance education as “teaching and planned learning in which teaching normally occurs in a different place from the learning, requiring communication through technologies, as well as special institutional organization”.

Figure 1: Ages and generations of distance education. Source: Casey, D. M. (2008). The Historical Development of Distance Education through Technology. *Tech Trends*, 52 (2), 45-51.

If one traces the history of distance education at the global level, it can be divided broadly into three ages viz. correspondence education, visual auditory education, and information communication technology (ICT) based education, and five generations, illustrated schematically in Figure 1. Earlier, only print media was used in the form of printed learning material, and the postal service was the only mode of correspondence. Thereafter, the age of audio and audio-visual came with the integration of audio-visual technologies in distance education. Subsequently, the age of ICT-based distance education emerged primarily due to advances in communication technologies, which has substantially widened the scope of distance education. Taylor has also described a similar conceptual framework of distance education as exhibited in Figure 2. India has quickly adapted these advancements and many Indian Universities have incorporated such ICT-based initiatives which have made distance education mode more interactive and accessible. But, there is a long way to go to bring an ever-increasing number of knowledge seekers to the fold of education.

Models of Distance Education and Associated Delivery Technologies	Characteristics of Delivery Technologies					
	Flexibility			Highly Refined Materials	Advanced Interactive Delivery	Institutional Variable Costs Approaching Zero
	Time	Place	Pace			
FIRST GENERATION The Correspondence Model • Print	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
SECOND GENERATION The Multimedia Model • Print	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
• Audiotape	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
• Videotape	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
• Computer-based learning (e.g. CML/CAL/IMM)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
• Interactive video (disk and tape)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
THIRD GENERATION The Telelearning Model • Audio tele-conferencing	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
• Video-conferencing	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
• Audiographic Communication	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
• Broadcast TV/Radio and audio-teleconferencing	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
FOURTH GENERATION The Flexible Learning Model • Interactive multimedia (IMM) online	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
• Internet-based access to WWW resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
• Computer mediated communication	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
FIFTH GENERATION The Intelligent Flexible Learning Model • Interactive multimedia (IMM) online	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
• Internet-based access to WWW resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
• Computer mediated communication, using automated response systems	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
• Campus portal access to institutional processes and resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Figure 2: Models of Distance Education- A Conceptual Framework. Source: Taylor, J. C. (2001). *Fifth generation distance education.* Higher Education Division, Department of

Education, Training and Youth Affairs, p. 3.

Defining attributes of distance education

Why do learners opt for distance mode of education?

- *Augmenting access and reach:* Overcoming the geographical, physical, and social constraints, distance mode of education is more accessible. It has largely succeeded in breaking down barriers and reaching increasingly more people than traditional education systems can. It largely eliminates the challenge of vast distances in India, allowing those in far-flung and rural areas to get a higher education without having to actually move. Furthermore, by being more flexible and often more affordable, it tackles social and economic obstacles that often prevent marginalized groups from accessing education. The “Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU)”, created to provide education for all, perfectly illustrates this by focusing on reaching out underprivileged populations, including those in remote areas, prisons, and economically disadvantaged regions. The expansion of open and distance learning (ODL) in India has been key in enabling millions of previously excluded learners to pursue higher education, significantly contributing to the nation's overall educational achievement. The rise of online platforms has further broadened this reach, pointing towards a major leveling of the playing field in higher education. This has the potential to boost socio-economic conditions in previously left out areas by equipping more individuals with the qualifications needed for better jobs and higher earnings.
- *Learner-centric flexibility and convenience:* Surmounting the inconvenience of the learners in terms of fixed schedule, place and pace of learning, the distance mode of education provides flexibility and convenience to the learners to control the time, pace, and place of their studies. This entails learners to accomplish their educational goals while fulfilling other commitments of their lives. Bijeesh (2017) has concluded that students who have paucity of time can go for distance education and pursue their education easily from their homes. Such an adaptability readily accommodates working professionals, homemakers, and individuals with diverse responsibilities. This evolution towards a more integrated and varied learning approach allows learners to incorporate education into their lives smoothly and without major upheaval. This inherent flexibility also supports the increasing importance of lifelong learning and continuous professional development, enabling individuals to gain new skills and qualifications throughout their careers and personal lives, unburdened by traditional academic timelines or the need for physical presence.
- *Making education affordable and cost effective:* Mitigating financial barriers in terms of costs involved in physical infrastructure, travel, logistics, etc. distance education makes education more affordable and cost effective, facilitating financial inclusion. This cost-effectiveness is particularly impactful for economically disadvantaged populations, allowing them to invest in their education and improve their opportunities for upward mobility.

- *Enhancing social equality and equity:* Distance mode of education provides opportunities to disadvantaged sections of the society like girl students who may not be otherwise allowed to physically attend colleges/universities for higher education due to prevalent conservative thinking or living far away from colleges/ universities.
- *Upgrading qualifications and/or professional skills:* There are many professionals who want to upgrade their qualifications and skills, but often not in a position to take leave from their jobs. The distance mode of education is a boon for such professionals. Further, distance education provides opportunities for students who had to discontinue their education due to various reasons such as poverty, family obligations etc.
- *Fostering an inclusive society:* Quite often, disabled students viz. physical, visual, hearing, etc. find it extremely difficult to receive education in physical mode. For such students, distance education offers a unique platform to meet their educational requirements, thus fostering an inclusive society.
- *Embracing Information Communication Technology for flexible learning:* Recent advances in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have fundamentally reshaped distance education, transforming it from primarily print-based correspondence into vibrant multimedia and online learning environments. The incorporation of diverse ICT tools, including video lectures, audio recordings, online discussion boards, and virtual classrooms, has enriched the learning experience, making it more interactive and engaging for students. Further, proactive government initiatives, such as SWAYAM, DIKSHA etc., have propelled and enabled technology-driven learning. This technological evolution has not only enhanced the delivery of educational content but has also broadened opportunities for enhanced interaction and collaboration between students and teachers, as well as among students themselves, effectively bridging the divide between traditional classroom settings and the distance learning experience.

Challenges facing distance education

While distance education in India offers numerous benefits, it also faces several significant challenges that need to be addressed to ensure its quality and reach. Researchers like Bernard et. al. (2004) suggest that several factors contribute to the lower achievement and higher dropout rates observed in distance education compared to traditional classroom settings. These include a lack of engagement with course material, financial constraints, insufficient feedback and support, feelings of isolation, low motivation, dissatisfaction with course requirements or regulations, and shifts in career aspirations. Some of the important challenges are summarized below.

- *Technological barriers:* A significant fraction of the Indian population, particularly in rural settings, is devoid of access to stable connectivity to internet and the necessary gadgets (personal computers, tablets, smartphones) for distance learning. This digital divide further adds to the existing inequalities. For instance, there was an estimate in 2021 that only 24% of households in rural India had internet access. Besides, the

Indian universities offering education in distance mode need to catch up with the recent developments in ICT based education. Digitization of library resources, development of quality learning material in the form of audio-video lectures by leading experts, robust learning management system (LMS) for providing an integrated and structured access to learners, etc. are among some key areas of immediate concern. Muralidharan et. al. (2019) have highlighted that there are challenges of using technology in education like teacher training, equal technological access to students, etc.

- *Curriculum Adaptation and Delivery:* The “National Education Policy (NEP)” 2020 emphasizes a multidisciplinary and flexible curriculum, with provisions of multiple entry and multiple exits. The policy emphasizes a paradigm shift away from rigid disciplinary boundaries, encouraging students to pursue a diverse range of subjects across arts, sciences, humanities, and vocational fields. There is a directed thrust on integration of vocational education with conventional programmes of study, providing students with practical skills alongside academic knowledge. An “Academic Bank of Credits (ABC)” is being developed to digitally store academic credits earned by students, facilitating credit transfer between different Higher Education Institutes and providing flexibility in completing degree programs. There is a great challenge ahead before the distance education providers to incorporate all important features of the NEP 2020, such as a choice and learning outcome-based curriculum framework, multidisciplinary approach of curriculum, multiple entry & multiple exits, etc., into their academic programmes so as to enable the distance learners to avail the maximum advantage of NEP 2020.
- *Limited face-to-face interaction:* Because of the lack of regular interaction between teacher and pupil, many times learners are unable to comprehend deep concepts which adversely affects their concept formation, resulting in a poor foundation for their higher academic pursuits. Brown (2017) has also found that the learning environment in distance education is limited as compared to traditional mode of education. As per Woodley (2004), limited interaction of distance learners with others in the college constitutes one of the reasons for poor academic achievements.
- *Assessment and Evaluation:* Improving assessment and evaluation in distance education is crucial for ensuring the quality and credibility of distance learning. Particularly, on the lines of face-to-face education programmes, there is a need to adopt formative and summative evaluation methods in distance learning programmes. To this end, the use of dedicated LMSs may play a crucial role. The LMSs are expected to not only act as virtual classrooms but also provide a platform to track the progress of distance learners in a systematic way.
- *Student support services:* Student support services in distance education are crucial for fostering student success and bridging the gap created by physical separation between learners and educational institutions. In the era of ever-increasing competition among students, the distance education system faces challenges to provide support services to students such as guidance and counselling in their academic and professional pursuits.

- *Inertia towards adaptation of emerging educational technologies:* Faculty members often resist in adopting new educational technologies, that impacts directly the teaching-learning process. This deprives the learners from the benefits of new educational technologies.
- *Distance learning vs. open learning:* In view of the emergence of different open learning platforms offering a variety of open educational resources (OERs) and certifications, the distance learning Institutes face the challenge of developing high quality digital learning modules for its learners. It seems to be a daunting and demanding task as OERs are often of global nature.
- *Handling professional/job-oriented programmes:* Rightly so, the Institutes offering distance learning programmes have introduced a good number of professional/ job-oriented programmes to meet the employability requirements of learners. These programmes are quite in demand. As the market needs generally change quite fast, the Institutes face the challenge of keeping the course curriculum of such programmes in synchronization with the market requirements.

Strengthening distance mode of education

- *Effective personal contact programme:* The personal contact programmes being conducted for distance education students should be effective and well organized. These should not only provide face-to-face interaction but also should have common discussion on various issues in the subject. Present policy of finishing syllabus during the PCP should be dispensed with. Only a few important issues should be discussed by the teachers. Otherwise, there should be tutorials and seminars during the PCP where the students could clear their doubts and difficulties by discussing the same with teachers.
- *Lesson writing improvement:* In today's globalized education landscape, writing of learning materials need to be improved to meet global standards because they directly affect students' learning experiences. The teachers should be given regular training in writing lessons for distance education students. Good printing will be an added dimension of lesson notes.
- *Student support services:* The student support services need to be strengthened. The syllabus should be given to a student, the moment he/she is admitted to a course; within a month, lesson notes should be dispatched and after that student should be regularly reminded of assignments. Many researchers have also suggested certain modifications in this regard. According to Katoch (2014), learner support services appear to be a significant weakness in India's ODL system, with over half of Distance Education Institutions (DEIs) lacking any such provisions. The distance education system provides distinct educational pathways for a wide class of learner groups, including those with special needs. Therefore, it must encompass its essential attributes such as flexibility, accessibility and varied learning experiences by providing efficient learning support. According to Tait (2003), support services play a vital role in developing confidence and self-esteem among learners, thereby steering a streamlined academic progress, decreasing dropout rates, and promoting a time-bound

accomplishment of their academic programmes. Simpson (2004, 2008) concluded that proactive interventions and motivating learners in open and distance education are helpful to successful learning accomplishments.

- *Robust feedback mechanism:* Proper feedback be given to the student on his/her assignments. At present such things are lacking in distance education. Asgar and Rampelli (2021) have emphasized the importance of conducting more workshops to train and orient faculty and support staff, thereby ensuring timely and effective services for learners. Functioning of the teachers should be reorganized in the distance education department. Their task requires many things. Therefore, they should not have only a few formal hours of working but should devote fully for the development of the distance education system in the university.
- *Motivating faculty for research:* Research component needs to be strengthened in the distance education institutions. The teachers in these institutions should be encouraged to undertake research projects to evaluate the efficacy of the ongoing distance education programmes, and research outputs should be properly analyzed for further improvements. Funding for some projects be made on priority basis to the teachers in distance education. It will help in improving the system and bringing it at par with the open learning system in the country.
- *Reinforcing study centres:* Study centres need to be organized as a part of distance education programmes. These will help the students to have good linkage with the university. The study centres need to be properly equipped with ICT gadgets to enable distance learners to utilize various learning resources offered by distance education institution.
- *Mitigating teacher-taught physical barrier:* Distance education inherently involves physical separation between students and teachers. However, this can be effectively overcome by promoting digital communication tools such as digital classroom platforms and various social media. These platforms offer learners valuable opportunities for direct interaction with teachers and facilitate discussions on academic challenges. Therefore, these resources should be strategically leveraged and prominently featured in the program's prospectus.
- *Technology integration:* To provide learners with up-to-date knowledge, distance education programmes should utilize diverse media such as digital learning resources, broadcasts, audio-visual content, and computers. All such media need to be integrated into a well-structured learning management system (LMS) of the distance learning institution. The learner should be free to choose the media according to the availability with the institution. Additionally, the LMS should include modules for submitting and grading learner assignments. Effective technology integration allows institutions to build more engaging and personalized distance learning programs, boosting student motivation. Karunanayaka and Naidu (2014) have advocated that integration of MOOCs/OER into distance and open universities support and motivate the student learning. Means et. al. (2010) have stressed the importance of technology to improve student outcomes in online learning. Earlier, Siemens (2005) have also emphasized the importance of technology in personalized learning pathways.

- *Faculty training:* To keep pace with ICT-related technological developments, it is equally important that the faculty members engaged in imparting distance education are provided adequate training opportunities to upgrade their pedagogical and professional skills.

Conclusion

Distance education has evolved significantly since its inception, offering flexible learning opportunities to learners globally. Despite its attributes it faces certain challenges like lack of face-to-face interaction, technical issues and self-motivation. The quality and effectiveness of distance education can be enhanced through the incorporation of strategies such as good learning resources, timely feedback, strong student support, and meaningful personal interactions. Murray and Kearsley (2011) suggested that effective interactive learning material in distance education can improve students' learning outcomes. Rovai (2022) talked about regular feedback and support services for strengthening the distance mode of education. Simonson (2014) stressed personalized learning and technological integration in the field of distance education. Zatonatska et. al. (2020) have rightly concluded in their study that although distance education may have unlimited future scope, yet there are still many issues to be further researched. Our study suggests that implementing effective strategies, distance education can provide high quality learning experiences and improve student learning outcomes.

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